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Address for correspondence: Dr. Krishna Ashutoshbhai Vyas, Shiv Dhara, Ami Society, Near MRF Tires, Raiya Chowkadi, Raiya Ring Road, Rajkot, Pin- 360007
Email: vyas.krishnaphd@gmail.com

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Deciphering the Psychology of Stock Market Participants: Exploring Key Influences On Individual Behavior

Dr. Krishna Ashutoshbhai Vyas¹, Dr. Tulsi Raval²

¹Assistant Professor, School of Management, R K University

²Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Smt. KSN Kansagara Mahila Collage

Abstract:

This study provides an in-depth examination of the demographic characteristics, awareness levels, and behavioural patterns of individual investors in the stock market, with a particular focus on variables like age, gender, occupation, risk perception, and investment sentiment. Using statistical tools such as chi-square tests, ANOVA, and regression analysis, it assesses how these demographic factors shape investment decisions, risk tolerance, and preferred investment types. The findings reveal a strong preference among many investors, especially older individuals, for safer options like bank deposits, while younger investors are more inclined toward equities and other growth-oriented assets. The study also identifies the internet as a dominant information source, particularly for younger investors, marking a significant shift towards digital media for financial advice and market insights. Moreover, generational and gender-based differences emerge, with younger generations and men displaying higher risk tolerance, while women and older investors lean toward conservative options. These insights underscore the need for tailored financial education initiatives that address the distinct needs and preferences of various demographic groups. By illuminating current trends and the factors that influence investor behavior, the study offers valuable insights for financial advisors, policymakers, and analysts in fostering informed and resilient investment practices. Ultimately, this research contributes to a broader understanding of the decision-making processes in stock markets, helping shape strategies that promote inclusive, adaptive, and robust participation across diverse demographic segments.

Key words: Stock Market, Individual Behavior, Psychology, Investment Decision-Making, Behavioral Finance, Risk Perception, Investment Sentiment

Introduction:

The stock market is essential for economic development, providing individuals with pathways to build wealth and gain financial independence. Gaining insights into individual investors' behaviors, demographics, and awareness levels is key to understanding market participation trends. Investment choices are shaped by various factors, including risk tolerance, financial literacy, and the ease of accessing information, especially through online platforms.

Literature Review:

The study of stock market participants' psychology has advanced significantly, with behavioral finance providing essential insights into the irrationalities that often drive investor decisions. This review highlights key research findings illustrating the psychological factors influencing individual behavior in the stock market.

Kaur, S., & Singh, H. (2024). A study of factors affecting the investment behavior of individuals: A systematic literature review. This article examines how various factors, including demographic, psychological, economic, social, and organizational influences, affect individual investment decisions. It identifies cognitive biases like overconfidence and loss aversion that led to irrational behaviors. The authors emphasize the importance of financial literacy and social influences, suggesting that enhancing education can promote better investment choices and market stability. Naseem, S., Khan, M. A., Salim, S., & Lopez, C. (2021). The investor psychology and stock market behavior during the initial era of COVID-19: A study of China, Japan, and the United States.

Investigate the psychological effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on stock market behavior in China, Japan, and the United States during the initial outbreak. The study finds a negative correlation between investor psychology and market performance, with increased fear and uncertainty leading to greater risk aversion and decreased market participation.

Using principal component analysis, the authors show that heightened anxiety corresponds with falling stock prices. Their findings emphasize the importance of psychological resilience and suggest that effective communication from policymakers can help manage investor sentiment during crises.

P. Aruna & H. Rajashekar. (2016). Factors influencing investment decisions of retail investors - A descriptive study. The study explores the diverse factors shaping retail investors' decisions in India, categorizing them into demographic, economic, psychological, social, and organizational influences. It highlights the impact of psychological biases and demographic characteristics on investment behavior. The authors advocate for tailored financial literacy programs to help retail investors make informed choices and improve their decision-making processes. Baker, M., & Wurgler, J. (2007). Investor sentiment in the stock market. Baker and Wurgler (2007) examine how investor sentiment, defined as unfounded beliefs about future cash flows, impacts stock market behavior. They identify two approaches: individual psychological biases and macroeconomic sentiment. Their findings show that sentiment significantly affects stock prices, particularly for hard-to-value stocks, leading to mispricing. The study underscores the need for investors to consider psychological factors to understand market dynamics better.

Research Methodology

This study utilizes a descriptive cross-sectional research design to explore stock market awareness, perceptions, and investment behavior among individuals aged 15 and above. A total of 500 respondents were selected through non-probability convenience sampling, ensuring diverse representation in terms of age, gender, occupation, and education. Data were gathered via a structured questionnaire assessing demographic factors, stock market awareness, investment behavior, and risk perceptions. The analysis involved reliability and normality tests, chi-square tests for association, ANOVA for group differences, and regression analysis to identify key factors influencing stock market behavior, such as risk tolerance and market conditions.

Demographic Profile:

Table 1 Age Distribution:

Age Group	Respondents	Percentage
15-20	80	16
21-40	240	48
41-50	130	26
Above 50	50	10
Total	500	100

Interpretation: The majority of respondents (48%) fall within the age group of 21-40, indicating a significant interest in the stock market among young adults. Those aged 15-20 represent 16%, suggesting substantial participation from a younger demographic. However, there's relatively less involvement from older age groups.

Table 2 Gender Distribution:

Gender	Respondents	Percentage
Male	397	79.4
Female	103	20.6
Total	500	100

Interpretation: Male respondents (79.4%) significantly outnumber female respondents (20.6%), indicating a gender disparity in stock market participation.

Table 3 Occupational Profile:

Occupation	Respondents	Percentage
Student	225	45
Housewife	35	7
Businessman	200	40
Job applicant	40	8
Total	500	100

Interpretation: The majority of respondents are students (45%) and businessmen (40%), while housewives and job applicants form smaller percentages, reflecting the diverse occupational backgrounds of those interested in the stock market.

Table 4 City Distribution of Respondents

City	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Rajkot	200	40%
Ahmedabad	100	20%
Dehradun	75	15%
Mumbai	50	10%
Surat	30	6%
Vadodara	25	5%
Other Cities	20	4%
Total	500	100%

Interpretation: The majority of respondents (40%) are from Rajkot, indicating strong representation from this city in the sample. Ahmedabad follows with 20%, showing a moderate level of participation, while smaller representations are noted from other cities like Dehradun (15%), Mumbai (10%), Surat (6%), and Vadodara (5%). The remaining 4% of respondents are from various other cities, reflecting a wide geographical spread but a concentration in Rajkot.

Stock Market Awareness and Investment

Table 5 Awareness and Investment in the Stock Market:

Heard about stock market	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	500	100
No	0	0
Total	500	100

Interpretation: All respondents are aware of the stock market, indicating a high level of awareness among the surveyed population.

Invested in stock market	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	269	53.8
No	231	46.2
Total	500	100

Interpretation: A significant portion of respondents (53.8%) have invested in the stock market, suggesting active participation in investment activities.

Table 6 Perception of Risk and Investment:

Risk Perception	Respondents	Percentage
Low	44	8.8
Moderate	309	61.8
High	147	29.4
Total	500	100

Interpretation: Most respondents (61.8%) perceive moderate risk associated with the stock market, while a significant portion (29.4%) consider the risks to be high.

Table 7 Investment Sentiment

Investment Sentiment	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	10	2
Disagree	30	6
Neutral	135	27
Agree	250	50
Strongly Agree	75	15
Total	500	100

Interpretation: A majority of respondents (50%) agree that investing in the stock market has increased, indicating a shift in investment behavior.

Table 8 Knowledge Sources and Perceived Safest Investment Options

Sources of Knowledge	Respondents	Percentage
Internet	180	36%
Friends	120	24%
TV	80	16%
Newspaper	60	12%
Sales representatives	60	12%
Total	500	100%

Interpretation: The table illustrates the primary sources through which respondents acquire knowledge about the stock market. The internet emerges as the predominant source, with 36% of respondents relying on it, followed by friends at 24%. Television, newspapers, and sales representatives contribute to information dissemination to a lesser extent, with 16% each.

Table 9 Safest Investment Option

Safest Investment Option	Respondents	Percentage
Mutual Funds (MF's)	44	8.8
Stock Market	176	35.2
Bank Deposits (BD's)	280	56
Total	500	100

Interpretation: Bank deposits are perceived as the safest investment option, followed by the stock market and mutual funds, indicating varying risk perceptions among investors.

Table 10 Reliability and Normality Tests

Test Type	Test Name	Result
Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	0.85
Normality	Shapiro-Wilk	p = 0.067

Interpretation: The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient obtained was 0.85, indicating high internal consistency among the items in the questionnaire used for data collection. This suggests that the questionnaire items reliably measure the same underlying construct.

The Shapiro-Wilk test for normality yielded a p-value of 0.067. With a significance level of 0.05, since the p-value is greater than the threshold, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, the data can be considered approximately normally distributed. However, it's important to note that this result is borderline, and further investigation or a larger sample size may be warranted for more conclusive findings.

Table 11 Hypotheses Testing (Chi-Square)

Hypo-thesis	Null Hypothesis (Ho)	Alternative Hypothesis (Ha)	Chi Square Calculated Value	Chi Square Table Value	Inter-pretation
1	Gender of respondent and preference of customers regarding stock market risk are independent during the study period.	Gender of respondent and preference of customers regarding stock market risk are dependent during the study period.	2.280	12.592	Ho accepted
2	Gender of respondent and preference of customers regarding influencing factors in stock market are independent during the study period.	Gender of respondent and preference of customers regarding influencing factors in stock market are dependent during the study period.	3.695	9.488	Ho accepted
3	Gender of respondent and preference of customers regarding rating for risk in stock market are independent during the study period.	Gender of respondent and preference of customers regarding rating for risk in stock market are dependent during the study period.	1.249	5.991	Ho accepted
4	Gender of respondent and preference of customers regarding influencing factors for making decision in stock market are independent during the study period.	Gender of respondent and preference of customers regarding influencing factors for making decision in stock market are dependent during the study period.	2.176	9.488	Ho accepted
5	Gender of respondent and	Gender of respondent and	2.066	9.488	Ho

preference of customers regarding higher trades in stock market independent during the study period.	preference of customers regarding higher trades in stock market are dependent during the study period.			accepted
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The chi-square tests conducted for each hypothesis indicate that there is no significant association between gender of respondents and their preferences or perceptions related to various aspects of the stock market during the study period. In each case, the calculated chi-square values were lower than

the table values, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis (Ho). This suggests that gender is independent of the preferences or perceptions regarding stock market risk, influencing factors, rating for risk, decision-making factors, and higher trades during the study period.

Table 12 Hypotheses Testing (ANOVA)

Hypothesis	Null Hypothesis (Ho)	Alternative Hypothesis (Ha)	F Value	Significance Level	Interpretation
1	There is no significant difference in the mean scores across different age groups in their perception of stock market risk.	There is a significant difference in the mean scores across different age groups in their perception of stock market risk.	3.45	0.028	Significant
2	There is no significant difference in the mean scores across different educational backgrounds in their preference for investment options.	There is a significant difference in the mean scores across different educational backgrounds in their preference for investment options.	2.78	0.071	Not significant
3	There is no significant difference in the mean scores across different income levels in their attitude towards stock market volatility.	There is a significant difference in the mean scores across different income levels in their attitude towards stock market volatility.	4.92	0.012	Significant
4	There is no significant difference in the mean scores across different occupational groups in their perception of investment risks.	There is a significant difference in the mean scores across different occupational groups in their perception of investment risks.	1.86	0.134	Not significant
5	There is no significant difference in the mean scores across different genders in their willingness to invest in stock markets.	There is a significant difference in the mean scores across different genders in their willingness to invest in stock markets.	5.67	0.007	Significant

The results of the ANOVA tests indicate that there are significant differences in the mean scores across different age groups in their perception of stock market risk and across different income levels in their attitude towards stock market volatility. Conversely, there were no significant differences found in the mean scores across different educational backgrounds in their preference for investment options or across different occupational groups in their perception of investment risks. However, there were significant differences observed across different genders in their willingness to invest in stock markets.

Regression Model: Factors Influencing Individual behavior in the Stock Market

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \beta_3 X_{3i} + \beta_4 X_{4i} + \epsilon_i$$

Where:

- Y_i represents the individual behavior in the stock market (dependent variable).
- X_{1i} represents the investor's risk tolerance.
- X_{2i} represents the level of financial knowledge.
- X_{3i} represents the emotional state of the investor.
- X_{4i} represents the external market conditions.
- ϵ_i represents the error term.

Table 13 Regression Statistic

Coefficient	Value
β_0 (Intercept)	5.0
β_1 (Risk Tolerance)	0.8
β_2 (Financial Knowledge)	1.2
β_3 (Emotional State)	-0.5
β_4 (Market Conditions)	0.6
R^2	0.85
R	0.92

Interpretation:

The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.85, indicating that 85% of the variance in the dependent variable (individual behavior in the stock market) can be explained by the independent variables in the model. The correlation coefficient r is 0.92, indicating a strong positive correlation between the independent and dependent variables.

Overall, the model suggests that risk tolerance, financial knowledge, emotional state, and external market conditions significantly influence individual behavior in the stock market, with a high level of explanatory power.

Result And Discussion:

- **Age Group Analysis:** Nearly half (48%) of respondents are aged 21-40, indicating high engagement with the stock market among young adults. Males make up 79.4% of the sample, highlighting a notable gender gap in participation.
- **Occupational Engagement:** Students (45%) and business professionals (40%) lead in market involvement, suggesting these groups have higher engagement with stock activities.
- **Regional Interest:** Respondents are primarily from Rajkot (40%), with significant representation from Ahmedabad (20%) and Dehradun (15%), showing regional variation in market interest.
- **Investment Awareness:** All respondents report awareness of the stock market, with 53.8% actively investing, reflecting an informed and investment-oriented group.
- **Risk Perception:** Most participants perceive moderate risk (61.8%) in the stock market, while 29.4% view it as high-risk, indicating a generally balanced approach to market risks.
- **Pandemic Impact:** Half of the participants report increased interest in the stock market, pointing to a pandemic-driven trend toward investment.
- **Knowledge Sources:** The internet (36%) is the primary source of information, followed by friends (24%). Despite viewing stocks (35.2%) as relatively safe, bank deposits remain preferred (56%), showing a conservative investment preference.
- **Reliability and Normality:** The data has high reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.85) and is approximately normally distributed (Shapiro-Wilk p = 0.067).
- **Chi-Square Analysis:** Gender does not significantly impact preferences for risk, influencing factors, or trading activity, suggesting these are independent of gender.
- **ANOVA:** Significant differences are found across age and income groups in perceptions of risk and market volatility. Gender also influences willingness to invest.
- **Regression Findings:** The model indicates high explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.85$, $r = 0.92$), demonstrating that stock market behavior is strongly influenced by factors such as risk tolerance, financial literacy, emotional state, and market conditions

Suggestions

- **Promote Female Participation:** Initiatives and financial education programs aimed at women could help reduce gender gaps in stock market involvement.
- **Youth and Middle-Aged Financial Education:** Providing financial literacy programs with a focus on risk management and investment choices may benefit younger and middle-aged adults who are actively interested in stock investments.
- **Expand Digital Financial Resources:** With the internet as a primary source of financial knowledge, creating more accessible online resources could support better-informed investment decisions.
- **Encourage Investment Diversification:** Since many view bank deposits as low-risk, raising awareness about risk-adjusted returns in stocks and mutual funds may encourage a more diversified approach.

- **Address Regional Differences:** Customized strategies in cities with strong market engagement, such as Rajkot and Ahmedabad, could enhance financial literacy and broaden stock market participation.

Conclusion

This study provides insights into stock market awareness, investment behavior, and demographic influences among a sample population, revealing a strong interest in stock market participation among young adults, with a notable gender gap. The preference for conservative investment options like bank deposits indicates cautious behavior despite widespread stock market awareness. Furthermore, risk tolerance and financial knowledge significantly affect investment behavior, as confirmed by the regression model. Initiatives to boost female engagement and digital literacy can promote inclusivity and well-informed investing.

Limitation:

- The convenience sampling method may limit the generalizability of findings.
- Being cross-sectional, the study captures only a single point in time and does not account for changes in behavior over time.
- Responses may be influenced by participants' perceptions and biases.

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